

A STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CONTINUOUS FIBER CERAMIC NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper reports two different areas of research in the field of nanocomposites. The first part reports on an analytical study for the prediction of mechanical properties of one of the constituents of nanocomposites; namely, nanotubes. The second part reports on the results of experiments on the influence of nano-fillers on the property enhancement of continuous fiber ceramic composites. In recent years, carbon nanotube reinforced composite materials have shown considerable developments and promises. In this study, we report constitutive models for the carbon nanotubes using asymptotic homogenization method. This method provides correct and mathematically justified results for the effective and local properties of composites with a periodic structure. In the experimental work, the effects of nanoparticles on mechanical performance of continuous fiber ceramic composites by preceramic polymer pyrolysis method have been investigated. Nanoparticle reinforced composite samples consistently showed marked improvements in flexural strength compared to their samples without nanoparticle reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: ceramic composites, carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, asymptotic homogenization, mechanical properties, preceramic polymer; nanoparticles; flexural test.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) exhibit remarkable mechanical properties significantly different from other engineering materials [1-6]. Yao and Lordi [2] studied the influence of the tube geometry on its modulus using molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and concluded that the torsional strain and, correspondingly, Young's modulus increases significantly with decreasing tube diameter and slightly with decreasing helicity. In their study, they also confirmed that Young's modulus of the nanotube is directly proportional to the wall thickness.

In order to explain the mechanical properties of carbon single walled nanotubes (SWNT) we have modelled the graphene sheet as a network structure containing hexagonal periodic cells. The physical behavior of such a heterogeneous medium with a regular periodic structure is governed by differential equations with rapidly oscillating coefficients dependent on the material properties of the individual components. Because of these coefficients, the relevant boundary value problems are extremely difficult to solve as they stand [7]. This makes it necessary to model the inhomogeneous medium by a set of simpler equations in which some averaged (or effective) coefficients would replace the exact ones. In general, our approach is based on the application of the general homogenization composite shell model developed earlier by Kalamkarov [7]. In the current research work, single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs) are modeled as a cylindrical network shell which in turn is considered as a non-homogeneous thin cylindrical 3D structure with zero material properties in the regions of perforation and

whose effective properties are estimated from the solution of the appropriate local problem set on the periodicity cell of the structure layer. Asymptotic homogenization method leads to the correct and mathematically justified results for effective and local properties of composites with a periodic structure, e.g., see [7, 8]. In the first part of this paper, we report the effective properties of carbon single-walled nanotubes and predict the structural dependence of nanotube modulus.

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) have many desirable high-temperature properties including high strength and modulus. CMCs and particularly Continuous Fiber Ceramic Composites (CFCCs) have attracted immense attention for use as high-temperature structural materials [9-11]. CFCCs are significantly tougher and more damage tolerant than their monolithic counterparts. However, even the best processed ceramic materials used in applications pose many unsolved problems; among them, relatively low fracture toughness and strength, degradation of mechanical properties at high temperatures, and poor resistance to creep, fatigue, and thermal shock. Dispersing metallic second-phase particles, preferably nano-sized particles, into ceramics improves their mechanical properties [6]. Compared to other size fillers, the advantage of using nanoparticles in composites is that the particle size and its distribution can be stabilized. A wide variety of properties, including magnetic, electric, thermal, and optical properties, can also be tailored in the composites due to the size effect of nano-sized dispersions. Such materials can be produced by incorporating a very small amount of nano-sized inclusion into the ceramic matrix. The preceramic polymer pyrolysis route to ceramic chemistry has attracted much attention as it offers a promising and cost-effective way to manufacture CMCs/CFCCs with little to no final machining [12-14] and parts with greater compositional homogeneity [15-16]. Preceramic polymers are organo-metallic polymers which, after curing, are chemically transformed during their pyrolysis step to yield a contributing ceramic phase(s) in the final ceramic part. In the second part of this study, we report on the integration of the concept of CFCC with that of nanocomposites, which is based on passive control of the microstructures by incorporating nanometer-size second-phase dispersions into the ceramic matrix of the CFCC.

PROPERTIES PREDICTION USING ASYMPTOTIC HOMOGENIZATION

Structure of Carbon Single-Walled Nanotubes

The combination of dimension, structure, and topology makes carbon nanotubes a special material and that translates the properties into an entire range of superior levels. Carbon nanotubes have a lattice-like structure that consists of periodic hexagonal cells of bonded carbon atoms; see Fig. 1 (a). The cross section of the open molecular lattice of carbon nanotube has no continuum thickness, although it has a closed cylindrical structure, see Fig. 1 (b). The geometric properties of nanotubes closely resemble those of cylindrical shells. In this study, the length of the C-C bond is represented by l . The adjacent carbon atoms are joined by a bar of circular cross section of diameter δ . A SWNT consists of many hexagonal carbon rings. The modeling of SWNTs is based on the application of the asymptotic homogenization techniques [7, 8].

Fig. 1: Periodic hexagonal cells of bonded carbon atoms

Asymptotic Homogenization Method Applied to Network Shells with Regular Structure

A mathematical framework from which to predict the mechanical behavior of regularly inhomogeneous media has been developed under the assumption that there is an ordered microstructure in such a media, describable by a small characteristic inhomogeneity dimension [7,8]. If we denote this dimension by δ , the partial differential equations of the problem have coefficients in form of $A(x/\delta) = A(y)$, which is a periodic function of its argument, and then the corresponding boundary value problem can be treated by asymptotically expanding the solution in powers of the small parameter δ employing the two-scale expansion technique known as the AHM [7, 8]. According to this method, two levels of spatial variables are considered, one for the microscopic description and the other variable for the macroscopic description of the process under study, and correspondingly the expansion coefficients are made to depend both on the slow macroscopic variable x and the rapid microscopic variable $y = x/\delta$. The former enables us to describe the global changes whereas the latter refers to the changes that take place at the local level.

In this model, the 3D local problem is formulated based on a single periodicity cell. The constitutive relations of the equivalent anisotropic homogeneous shell, that is between the stress resultants N_{11} , N_{22} (normal), and N_{12} (shear) on one hand, and the mid-surface strains ε_{11} , ε_{22} (elongations), ε_{12} (shear) on the other, can be represented as the following [7, 17]:

$$N_{\alpha\beta} = \delta \langle b_{\alpha\beta}^{\lambda\mu} \rangle \varepsilon_{\lambda\mu} + \delta^2 \langle b_{\alpha\beta}^{*\lambda\mu} \rangle k_{\lambda\mu} \quad (1)$$

where each α , β , λ and μ take values 1 and 2 and repeated indices λ and μ are summed. The angle brackets in Eq. (1) denote averaging (of stiffness) by integration over the 3D periodicity cell of the composite layer.

Shell structures obtained from spatially periodic network reinforcements have found numerous applications in many branches of modern engineering [7, 8, 18]. If the network structure is dense enough, it has been shown that the mechanical behavior of such a structure can be well predicted by means of a continuum model. The actual network is then visualized as a continuous shell with elastic constitutive relation of some special generally anisotropic form. Let the periodicity cell of the network shell be formed by N bars. Assume that a bar with a number j ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$) makes an angle φ_j with the coordinate line α_1 and that it is made of isotropic material with Young's modulus E_j and Poisson's ratio ν_j , and that the volume fraction of this bar within the periodicity cell is γ_j , see Fig. 2. Subsequently, the effective stiffnesses of the whole homogenized network shell can be determined by summing over all N bars.

Fig. 2: Bar number j within the periodicity cell of a network shell.

It has been shown that the local problems of the bar can be solved analytically for arbitrary cross-section of the bar [7]. For the purpose of modeling the SWNT, one needs to consider only cylindrical shells and circular cross-sections of the bars forming the periodicity cell. For a cylindrical shell, the coordinate line α_1 is defined as the circumferential coordinate and the coordinate line α_2 is defined as the longitudinal axis. In conformity with the above, the following relations are valid [10]:

$$\langle b_{\alpha\beta}^{\lambda\mu} \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^N E_j B_j^{\alpha\beta\lambda\mu} \gamma_j \quad (2)$$

$$\langle z b_{\alpha\beta}^{*\lambda\mu} \rangle = \sum_{j=1}^N E_j \left(B_j^{\alpha\beta\lambda\mu} + \frac{C_j^{\alpha\beta\lambda\mu}}{1+\nu_j} \right) \frac{\gamma_j}{16} \quad (3)$$

where $\langle z b_{\alpha\beta}^{\lambda\mu} \rangle = \langle b_{\alpha\beta}^{*\lambda\mu} \rangle = 0$. The functions $B_j^{\alpha\beta\lambda\mu}$ and $C_j^{\alpha\beta\lambda\mu}$ in Eqs. (2) and (3) depend on the fourfold index combination $\alpha\beta\lambda\mu$ and are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} B_j^{1111} &= \cos^4 \varphi_j & C_j^{1111} &= \cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j \\ B_j^{2222} &= \sin^4 \varphi_j & C_j^{2222} &= \cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j \\ B_j^{1212} &= \cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j & C_j^{1212} &= \frac{1}{4} (\cos^4 \varphi_j + \sin^4 \varphi_j - 2 \cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j) \\ B_j^{1122} &= B_j^{2211} = \cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j & C_j^{1122} &= C_j^{2211} = -\cos^2 \varphi_j \sin^2 \varphi_j \\ B_j^{1112} &= B_j^{1211} = \cos^3 \varphi_j \sin \varphi_j & C_j^{1112} &= C_j^{1211} = \frac{1}{2} (\cos \varphi_j \sin^3 \varphi_j - \cos^3 \varphi_j \sin \varphi_j) \\ B_j^{1222} &= B_j^{2212} = \cos \varphi_j \sin^3 \varphi_j & C_j^{1222} &= C_j^{2212} = \frac{1}{2} (\cos^3 \varphi_j \sin \varphi_j - \cos \varphi_j \sin^3 \varphi_j) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Asymptotic Homogenization Modeling Applied to SWNT

This part of the paper explains the development of constitutive equations of SWNT using the above obtained solutions for the homogenized cylindrical network shells of periodic structure. The SWNT is modeled by a cylindrical network shell made of hexagonal periodicity cell shown in Fig. 3. The C-C bond is modeled by bars as shown in Fig. 3. We assume that these bars have the same material parameters E , ν and α^T and that they have circular cross sections.

Applying Eq. (2) and (3) to the periodicity cell of SWNT, see Fig. 3, we can calculate all effective stiffnesses entering the constitutive relation, Eq. (1), as coefficients. As a result, we have obtained the following constitutive relations of the homogenized SWNT for Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Periodicity cell of a SWNT

$$N_{11} = \delta^2 \frac{E}{l} \frac{\pi}{16\sqrt{3}} (3\varepsilon_{11} + \varepsilon_{22}), \quad N_{22} = \delta^2 \frac{E}{l} \frac{\pi}{16\sqrt{3}} (\varepsilon_{11} + 3\varepsilon_{22}) \quad \text{and} \quad N_{12} = \delta^2 \frac{E}{l} \frac{\pi}{16\sqrt{3}} \varepsilon_{12} \quad (5)$$

The above obtained constitutive relation given by Eq. (5) can be further employed to describe mechanical behavior of SWNT in any particular mechanical situations, explained in the following.

Engineering Constants of SWNT

In this section, we derive the closed form solutions for engineering constants of a SWNT. The matrix form of Eq. (5) can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_{11} \\ N_{22} \\ N_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \delta^2 \frac{E}{l} \frac{\pi}{16\sqrt{3}} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Inverting Eq. (6) and applying a load $N_{11} \neq 0$, $N_{22} = 0$, $N_{12} = 0$ we obtain:

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{6\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \left(\frac{l}{\delta E} \right) \left(\frac{N_{11}}{\delta} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon_{22} = -\frac{6}{\pi\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{l}{\delta E} \right) \left(\frac{N_{11}}{\delta} \right) \quad (7)$$

The effective modulus in the α_1 direction, E_{11} is given by Eq. (8):

$$E_{11} = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{\varepsilon_{11}} = \frac{\left(\frac{N_{11}}{\delta} \right)}{\varepsilon_{11}} = \frac{\pi}{6\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{\delta E}{l} \right) \quad (8)$$

Following the same procedure used for calculating E_{11} , we can find relation for the effective modulus in the α_2 direction, by applying load $N_{22} \neq 0$, $N_{11} = 0$, $N_{12} = 0$.

$$E_{22} = \frac{\sigma_{22}}{\varepsilon_{22}} = \frac{\left(\frac{N_{22}}{\delta} \right)}{\varepsilon_{22}} = \frac{\pi}{6\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{\delta E}{l} \right) \quad (9)$$

It is interesting to note that the effective moduli of the structure are the same in directions α_1 and α_2 . Therefore, based on the pattern of arrangement of periodicity cells in the SWNT either E_{11} or E_{22} , which are proven to be the same, would serve as the Young's modulus of the SWNT along the longitudinal direction (E_{SWNT}).

$$E_{SWNT} = \frac{\pi}{6\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{\delta E}{l} \right) \quad (10)$$

It merits notice from Eq. (10) that the Young's modulus of nanotube increases with increasing bar diameter (δ). In fact, in our modeling the thickness of the tube is assumed to

be the same as the diameter of the bar, which in turn points out that the Young's modulus of SWNT increases with increasing tube wall thickness which is consistent with the observations in [2]. The diameter of the SWNT would decrease with decreasing bar length (l). From Eq. (10), it can be observed that the Young's modulus of nanotube increases with decreasing C-C link length (l), which in other words can be interpreted as the Young's modulus of SWNT increases with decreasing tube diameter (d). Once again, this dependency of Young's modulus tube diameter of SWNT is consistent with other published works, e. g., see [2].

MANUFACTURING AND TESTING OF CONTINUOUS FIBER CERAMIC NANOCOMPOSITES

Details on the manufacturing process have already been reported by the same authors [19]. The inorganic polymer used in this study was KiON CERASET® preceramic polymer [20]. The final composition of the composite depends on the pyrolysis cycle and inert gas used. In the present work, nitrogen gas was used to produce silicon carbide matrix. Nicalon™ ceramic fiber was chosen as the fiber system reinforcement. The nano-sized inclusions were ceramic and metal nanoparticles. Five different nanoparticles were used: silicon carbide (SiC), carbon (C), titanium oxide (TiO₂), yttrium oxide (Y₂O₃), and zinc oxide (ZnO). All these particles are insoluble in water and stable in air. Table 1 gives the specifications of the five different nanoparticles employed in this study.

Table 1: Specifications of Nanoparticles used for CFCC reinforcement.

	TiO ₂	ZnO	Y ₂ O ₃	C	SiC
Density(g/cc)	0.04 - 0.06	5.606	1	0.336	0.069
Particle size(nm)	15	20	29	30	45-55
Surface Area (m ² /gm)	190-290	50	42	>100	70-90

In the following, Ni/CE refers to a CFCC that is not reinforced with nanoparticles and will be considered as a base material. Ni/CE-n refers to a base composite reinforced with any Nanoparticle, say “n”, manufactured with preceramic polymer pyrolysis/reinfiltration route where the initial matrix has nanoparticles but reinfiltration matrix does not. Ni/CE-n-R-n refers to a Ni/CE composite that uses matrix reinforced nanoparticle “n” for both fabrication and subsequent reinfiltrations.

In the post processing analysis [19], the void content for samples without nanoparticles were found to be well below 4% indicating a good part quality (part with void volume fraction below 5% is well accepted for ceramics). For samples with nanoparticles, a detailed characterization study is in progress; however, our initial study [19] revealed no marked difference in the porosity content between base materials and those with nanoparticles. All CFCC samples manufactured without and with nanoparticles took the same number of pyrolysis/reinfiltration cycles to achieve the weight convergence [19]. This suggests that the nanoparticle reinforcements do not cause premature closures.

Four-point Bending Test Results and Discussion

The main objective of this part of the study is to experimentally evaluate the performance of different CFCC specimens in flexure. A four-point bend fixture was used to measure the flexural load-deflection response of CFCC specimens loaded in four-point bending. In this study, the span/thickness ratio is 43.5. All specimens were nominally 180 mm long, 12.7 mm wide, and

3.67 mm thick. Five samples were used for each type of CFCC flexure test. The tests were conducted using an Instron load testing machine.

Three different types of CFCC samples, Ni/CE (base), Ni / CE-n, and Ni/CE-n-R-n were tested, with five samples from each category. Four-point bending test was chosen to quantify the performance of the CFCCs. For obtaining a valid flexural strength by four-point bending test, a high support span/thickness (L/d) ratio of 45 was used to prevent shear failure and invalidation of the tests. Figure 4(a) shows a typical stress-microstrain curve obtained in the four-point bending tests. The strain was calculated at the mid-span of the test specimen as suggested in the ASTM standard [21]. The failure stress is at the peak in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: a) Typical stress-strain curve of Ni/CE, and b) Typical sample failed at its mid-span in four-point bending test.

All the samples tested fractured inside the uniformly stressed region of flexure specimen (between the inner loading points of the fixture), eliminating uncertainties about failures due to stress concentrations outside the uniform loading region as well as the shear failure of the specimen, see Fig. 4(b). The flexural strengths and moduli for all samples from the four-point bend test are reported in Table 2 with their standard deviations in the parentheses.

Table 2: Flexure strengths and moduli for Ni/CE, Ni/CE-n, and Ni/CE-n-R-n type CFCCs.

CFCC	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	CFCC type	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
Ni /CE	31.85 (1.06)	95.14 (3.90)	Ni/CE	31.85 (1.06)	95.14 (3.90)
Ni/CE-TiO ₂	35.16 (2.72)	69.60 (2.35)	Ni/CE-TiO ₂ -R-TiO ₂	29.87 (1.48)	71.44 (2.84)
Ni/CE-ZnO	38.19 (0.84)	76.14 (6.04)	Ni/CE -ZnO-R-ZnO	38.81 (2.51)	73.57 (4.47)
Ni/CE-Y ₂ O ₃	33.30 (4.05)	88.15 (13.13)	Ni/CE-Y ₂ O ₃ -R-Y ₂ O ₃	39.20 (2.30)	87.21 (11.76)
Ni/CE-C	35.83 (2.57)	89.26 (9.00)	Ni/CE-C-R-C	36.46 (2.57)	87.18 (6.32)
Ni/CE-SiC	33.55 (4.91)	74.18 (11.5)	Ni/CE-SiC-R-SiC	33.54 (2.17)	67.09 (8.24)

Analyzing the data in Table 2, a consistent and significant reduction in modulus and the general tendency of increase in flexural strength when CFCCs are filled with nanoparticles

are observed. Moreover, for both Ni/CE-n and Ni/CE-n-R-n type CFCCs a general tendency of decrease in flexural strength with increasing particle size could be observed with some exceptions. It should also be mentioned that the CFCC flexural strength improves significantly with nanoparticle reinforced preceramic polymer reinfiltration route, except in the case of Ni/CE-TiO₂-R-TiO₂, see Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: CFCC strength enhancement for various types of nanocomposites.

The reason for the reduction in flexural strength of Ni/CE-TiO₂-R-TiO₂ may be attributed to the very small size (15nm) and large surface area of TiO₂ nanoparticles resulting in problems associated with uniform dispersions, compared to larger nanoparticles. Overall, while Ni/CE-TiO₂-R-TiO₂ performed the worst, Ni/CE-Y₂O₃-R-Y₂O₃ performed the best in a balance of strength and modulus. It should also be mentioned that while, in general the strength increased, the modulus decreased with the addition of nanoparticles to CFCCs, see Table 2.

CONCLUSIONS

Governing relations leading to the mechanical properties prediction of carbon single-walled nanotubes were derived using the asymptotic homogenization method. The derived formulae make it easy to understand the dependencies of these mechanical properties of SWNT on its geometrical parameters. Based on our results, it is inferred that the Young's modulus of a single-walled nanotube increases with decreasing tube radius and increasing effective wall thickness of the tube. In an experimental study of nanocomposites, three different systems of continuous fiber ceramic composites were manufactured following preceramic polymer pyrolysis route. One base sample without nanoparticle reinforcement and the two other types with nanoparticle reinforcing but they differed in the reinfiltration cycle. A characterization analysis of the samples using scanning electron microscopy revealed excellent quality of the parts. The composite samples have revealed compactness and retention of shape. Four-point bending test was performed to evaluate the mechanical performance of the ceramic composites samples at room temperature. In general, nanoparticles reinforced samples consistently showed significant improvement in flexural strength compared to their counterparts without nanoparticle reinforcement. A significant and consistent reduction in modulus was observed for nanoparticles filled CFCCs compared to the base CFCC material.

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REFERENCES

1. Harik, V.M., "Ranges of Applicability for the Continuum-beam Model in the Constitutive Analysis of Carbon Nanotubes: Nanotubes or Nano-beams?," NASA/CR-2001-211013 ICASE Report No. 2001-16, ICASE, Hampton, VA, 2001.
2. Yao, N., and Lordi, V., "Young's Modulus of Single-Walled Carbon Nanotubes," *Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 84, No. 4, 1998, pp. 1939-1943.
3. Liu, J.P., "Elastic Properties of Carbon Nanotubes and Nanoropes," *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 79, No. 7, 1997, pp. 1297-1300.
4. Treacy, M.M.J., Ebbesen, T.W., and Gibson, J.M., "Exceptionally High Young's Modulus Observed for Individual Carbon Nanotubes," *Nature*, Vol. 381, 1996, pp. 678 – 680.
5. Ozaki, T., Iwasa, Y., and Mitani, T., "Stiffness of Carbon Single-Walled Nanotubes Under Large Strain," *Physics Review Letter*, Vol. 84, No. 8, 2000, pp. 1712-1715.
6. Ajayan, P.M., Schadler, L.S., and Braun, P.V., *Nanocomposite Science and Technology*, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2003.
7. Kalamkarov, A.L., *Composite and Reinforced Elements of Construction*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd., Chichester, NY, 1992.
8. Kalamkarov, A.L., and Kolpakov, A.G., *Analysis, Design and Optimization of Composite Structures*, John Wiley & Sons Ltd., Chichester, NY, 1997.
9. Hench, L.L., and Ulrich, D.R., *Ultra-structure Processing of Ceramics, Glasses and Composites*, New York, NY, John Wiley Publishing Co., 1984.
10. Prewo, M. K., Brennan, J. J., and Layden, G. K., "Fiber-reinforced Glasses and Glass-Ceramics for High Performance Applications," *American Ceramic Society Bulletin*, 65(2):305-322, 1989.
11. Prewo, M. K., "Fiber-Reinforced Ceramics: New Opportunities for Composite Materials," *American Ceramic Society Bulletin*, 68(2):395-400, 1989.
12. Jamet, J., Spann, J. R., Rice, R. W., Lewis, D., and Coblenz, W. S., "Ceramic-Fiber Composite Processing via Polymer-Filler matrices," *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.* 5(7-8):677-694, 1984.
13. Rogers, J. J., Semen, J., and Yu, Y.-F., "Silicon Carbide and Silicon Nitride Structural Ceramics Derived from a Pre ceramic Polymer Binder," *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.*, 10(7-8): 833-836, 1989.
14. Semen, J., and Loop, J. G., "Structural Ceramics Derived from a Pre ceramic Polymer," *Ceram. Eng. Sci. Proc.*, 11(9-10):1387-1394, 1990.
15. Ghasemi-Nejhad, M.N., Chandramouli, M.V., and Yousefpur, A., "Processing and performance of Continuous Fiber Ceramic Composites by Pre ceramic Polymer Pyrolysis: I – Filament Winding," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 35(24):2207-2237, 2001.
16. Ghasemi-Nejhad, M.N., Bayliss, J.K., and Yousefpur, A., "Processing and performance of Continuous Fiber Ceramic Composites by Pre ceramic Polymer Pyrolysis: II – Resin Transfer Molding," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 35(24):2239-2255, 2001.
17. Kalamkarov, A.L., Veedu, V.P., and Ghasemi-Nejhad, M.N., "Mechanical Properties Modeling of Carbon Single-Walled Nanotubes: An Asymptotic Homogenization Method," *Journal of Computational and Theoretical Nanoscience*, American Scientific Publishers, Vol. 2, No. 1, 2005.
18. Kalamkarov, A.L., "On the determination of effective characteristics of cellular plates and shells of periodic structure," *Mechanics of Solids*. Vol. 22, No. 2, 1987, pp. 175-179.

19. Gudapati, V., Veedu, V.P., and Ghasemi-Nejhad, M.N., "Polymeric Precursor Pyrolysis for Flexural Property Evaluation of Continuous Fiber Ceramic Nanocomposites," *Journal of Composite Science and Technology*, 2005, (in press).
20. Product Data Sheet KiON CERASET® Polyureasilazane, KiON Corporation, Huntingdon Valley, PA, U.S.A., 2004.
21. ASTM standard: C1341-97, Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Continuous Fiber-Reinforced Advanced Ceramic Composites, Vol. 15.01: 509-526, 2004.